

This is a link to the data repository refubium, which hosts the experimental data acquired for the paper "Quantum spins and hybridization in artificially-constructed chains of magnetic adatoms on a superconductor" by Liebhaber, Eva; Rütten, Lisa M.; Reecht, Gael; Steiner, Jacob F.; Rohlf, Sebastian; Rosnagel, Kai; von Oppen, Felix; Franke, Katharina J., published in Nature Communications 13, 2160 (2022)

<https://refubium.fu-berlin.de/handle/fub188/34309>